

CITY SOUND & EMOTION

THE CITY UNDERSTOOD AS AN EMOTIONAL SCENARIO FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF SOUND

Ivan Chaparro, Ricardo Dueñas

✉ ivanf.chaparro@utadeo.edu.co, info@resoundcity.com

ABSTRACT

This workshop is the result of a practice-based research, which explored several interrelated elements: first the theory of Psychogeography, applied to the creative representation of urban environments from a multilayered approach and from an emotional and psychological perspective; second, the exploration of sound and acoustic theory, as research tools and artistic possibilities, directed towards the analysis of public space, its documentation and understanding in relation to processes of identity, intangible patrimony and storytelling. And finally, an experimentation and technical research related to audio postproduction, real-time data processing and interactivity. This exploration lead altogether to the design of a persuasive experience that sought to communicate the research outcomes to a broader audience by means of an experimental performance and sound installation presented initially in several cities in the north of Europe.

BACKGROUND

This workshop is the result of a practice-based research which explored several interrelated elements: first the theory of Psychogeography, applied to the creative representation of urban environments from a multilayered approach and from an emotional and psychological perspective; second, the exploration of sound and acoustic theory, as research tools and artistic possibilities, directed towards the analysis of public space, its documentation and understanding in relation to processes of identity, intangible patrimony, and storytelling. And finally, an experimentation and technical research related to audio postproduction, real-time data processing and interactivity. This exploration lead altogether to the design of a persuasive experience that sought to communicate the research outcomes to a broader audience by means of an experimental performance and sound installation presented initially in several cities in the north of Europe.

Please take a few minutes to watch a trailer of one the previous performances carried out in Stockholm for an international art fair related to urban studies:

<http://www.resoundcity.com/human-mind-as-a-city/>

AIM

The main aim of the workshop is to illustrate the way in which the city, understood as a multifaceted system, can be abstracted and represented in relation to human emotions and therefore as a psychological-auditory scenario.

Different ways of walking through the city mean different narratives and perspectives and consequently different ways of thinking urban spaces.

APPROACH

The Workshop is divided in 5 stages as follows:

1. Introduction to the concept of Fragmentality (1 hour): namely, a form of urban exploration and documentation that involves walking by foot the streets of a given city collecting fragments in order to generate a posterior dialectical image through several methods of analysis. This initial stage is highly influenced by the practice of *flânerie* from the poet Charles Baudelaire, the work of the philosopher Walter Benjamin, the theory of Psychogeography,

the Situationist techniques and recent inter and trans-disciplinary practices carried out mainly in the north of Europe. All of them are taken as conceptual basis that outline the acts of walking and collecting as social and aesthetic disciplines.

2. The Derive (2.5 hours): Based on the conceptual basis outlined in the 1st stage, in the second step, the workshop participants have to stroll the streets in groups, following a simple set of rules while documenting their impressions with short text entries and sound clips. In order to capture the latter it is required of the participants that they have smartphones with GPS-logging and audio-recording features.
 - a. Sound collection: right after the workshop participants get back from their 'Derive', the organizers will collect and organize the audio files they collected in a collective archive; this will be the raw material for the final interactive experience.
3. Analysis and Storytelling (1 hour): the Derive carried out in the previous step is followed by a group discussion in which the impressions are shared and contrasted. Through several ideation techniques the goal is to generate a few collective narratives out of the short fragments of text collected during the walks.
4. Socialization and narrative crowd-ideation (1 hour): at this stage the different groups share the result of their impressions in the form of narratives, graphics, images, videos and so forth. Thereafter, the idea is to create a single narrative out of the stories presented by the different groups.
5. Interactive sound-experience (30 minutes): following the overall concept, the final stage is an experimental performance in which the audio-clips provided by the participants become the fragments in a collective and interactive composition, where the resulting soundscape responds to the brain activity of one of the participants, while connected to a neural actuator, therefore controlled by his or her emotions. The participant would be reading aloud the co-created narrative while the sound outcome would be matching his mental wandering through the text.

By using a Brain Interface, the concept of the final experience illustrates metaphorically the core of Psychogeographical theory, that is, a 'topographical model' that compares the human psyche with an imagined space, in order to make its complexity understandable. We intend to do the opposite, to create a sound-imagined space out of urban fragments, out of the brain activity of a person while performing a series of activities. It will be like thinking of a map from a given territory, which helps us to understand its geography, which, both like a mind or a city, has conscious, subconscious and unconscious areas.

The resulting performance would be a metaphorical Derive through a collection of urban sounds gathered collectively, by means of a brain scan device that measures specific brain waves while creating the sound composition.

NAMES, CONTACT AND AFFILIATIONS

Ivan Chaparro (primary contact)

Creative Director

Resoundcity Art Lab
www.resoundcity.com

Associate Professor

Jorge Tadeo Lozano University
Faculty of Arts and Design

Mobile: (+57) 319 2573243

emails: info@resoundcity.com

ivanf.chaparro@utadeo.edu.co

Ricardo Dueñas

Chief Technology Officer

Resoundcity Art Lab
www.resoundcity.com

Mobile: (+57) 317 8436111

email: info@resoundcity.com,

INTENDED NUMBER OF ATTENDEES (MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM)

Min 10, max 30

PLANNED DURATION OF THE WORKSHOP

full-day (6 hours)

PREFERRED CITIES

Medellín or Bogotá

SPACE/ROOM NEEDED TO CONDUCT THE WORKSHOP

1. A room for a screening, following debate and sound-performance:
2. Necessary equipment
 - a. Projector
 - b. Four studio sound-monitors (speakers) similar to these ones: <http://amzn.to/1fQJBb6>
 - c. Wires and connectors suitable to distribute them along the room, preferably in each corner (the idea would be to simulate the perception of spatial movement through a quadrasonic sound system)

MATERIALS AND SPECIAL REQUIREMENTS NEEDED FOR THE WORKSHOP

The assistants require the following equipment and tools:

1. A smartphone suitable for recording sound-clips in wav format
2. Headphones
3. Drawing materials: color-pencils, color-pens, markers

Ivan Chaparro

Designer and artist from Colombia, his artistic practice is located in the space between art, architecture, design and social research; considering technological media as wide, open-textured tools that help to reveal relations between material production and culture. Currently he is working as creative director of RESOUNDCITY and as associate professor at Jorge Tadeo Lozano University.

Ricardo Dueñas

Electronic Engineer from Bogotá, Colombia. Develops software and hardware for interactive installations and technology-driven art projects. Is co-founder of RESOUNDCITY, an urban research artistic laboratory. His recent works are related to e-textiles, sound art and dance.